

FORMATION OF LINGUISTIC COMPETENCIES IN TEACHING PARONYMOUS WORDS GIVEN IN MOTHER LANGUAGE AND READING LITERACY TEXTBOOK

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Annotation: Enriching the vocabulary of elementary school students with paronyms practical issues of formation of speech competences the issues of appropriate use of paronymous words in the speech process are covered.

Key Words: Competence, paronyms, language, linguistics, pronunciation.

It is known that in raising the young generation, we are not limited to education, but all of us are equally responsible for making them a necessary person for the society in all aspects. If we start developing the outlook, independent thinking, and speech of the future generation from the primary school age, these children will have no difficulty in finding their place in society in the future. The current aspect of the current educational reforms is that young people who can think independently, have a broad outlook, are armed with modern knowledge, are creative, talented, can choose their own direction, and can prove their own views, to form the skills of preparation for an independent life. the result of the educational content is clearly visible. Students who have just entered school are not given pens and notebooks, because their ideas about education, school, and lessons have not yet been fully formed. Talking with children within the framework of the topics they know, children's love and interest towards the interlocutor is created. Pronounces speech sounds in the Uzbek language correctly, can follow the rules of pronunciation and the rule of syllabification. To use the acquired lexical units in the text, to express the words related to the topic appropriately in oral and written speech, to be able to use the grammatical forms of words correctly in speech, to use punctuation marks correctly, observes the rules of syllabification, observes the rules of pronunciation, learns the correct use of words related to the topic in oral and written speech. Such mastering creates a competence approach in modern education. Competence is Latin for achieving, worthy, deserving. Linguistic foundations of teaching are described in standards, programs and textbooks, reflecting the educational content of linguistics of communicative competence. Knowledge, experience, oratory or linguistic competence in one or another field forms the skills and abilities to speak freely in the speech process. The problem of formation of linguistic competence in students is one of the most important issues in introducing the science of mother tongue and reading literacy, and there are different solutions to this problem. Linguistic competence includes mastering phonetic, orthographic, lexical, grammatical knowledge and develops students' speaking ability. Linguistic competence is based on two components:

- knowledge based on taught rules;
- ability to understand speech and communicate.

It is not enough to develop only linguistic competence to form students' speaking skills. Speech skills include linguistic and communicative competence, that is, knowledge about the language system and its structure; to have a system of information on the structure of the

language: phonetics, vocabulary, word structure and word formation, morphology, syntax and the basics of speech styles; the ability to use the language system in practice, etc. Learning about the language system does not happen by itself. In the process of formation of linguistic competence, it is important to develop the personality of the student, his ability to use his knowledge of the studied language system. That is, linguistic competence implies the acquisition of knowledge about language material (phonetics, lexicon, grammar) and types of speech activity (listening, speaking, reading and writing). This is done step by step. It is necessary to teach children to think freely, to speak beautifully and fluently, and during this time to partly correct and reform their mistakes. In order to start enriching their vocabulary, children who have just entered primary school learn the scope of various regional words in the process of communicating with their environment, lifestyle, and family. And we develop students' linguistic competences and the ability to use speech units such as adverbs, homonyms, paronyms, etc. Adherence to pronunciation standards, rules of moving syllables, being able to use words correctly and appropriately in oral and written speech, being able to use grammatical forms of words correctly in speech. If these skills are formed in students during the literacy training period, they will be able to use pictorial and imaginative methods when teaching new words to children. In our speech, there are words that differ by one sound. Such words have two different meanings in speech. But we can use these words correctly only when we say the information required by the speech during the speech process. The words used in oral speech mainly differ in one sound and have different meanings. In linguistics, such words are called paronymous words. Paronyms are words whose pronunciation, sound and morpheme structure are similar, and whose lexical meanings are different or partially close. Competency approach in paronym words has attracted the attention of today's linguists. The problem of paronymy arises as a result of deliberately bringing paronyms together in speech or misusing them without knowing their meaning (speech error). This phenomenon is common among elementary school students. In the 3rd grade mother tongue and reading literacy textbook, paronyms are explained on the topic "There is a difference between a word and a word". In task 1 on page 37 of the textbook:

The horn of the ram was broken.

The king issued a new decree. The difference between the words "horn" and "king" is the sound "x" and "h". The word "Shokh" expressed in task 1 on page 37 of this textbook is explained as follows in the "Five-volume annotated dictionary of the Uzbek language".

Horn I. Persian - branch, branch, branch. 1 A shoot is a growth that grows sideways from the trunk of a tree or bush. Cut a branch of a tree. 2 A broken, cut branch, twig or branch.

Horn II - horn, horn A hard bony growth that grows from the head of some animals; ice cream
The second word we are comparing is shah, and several meanings of this word are given in the explanatory dictionary.

The king is the king. 1 min. king (khan king. 2. In the game of chess: the most important figure. 3 In the game of chess: an attack is made directly on the opponent's king with a piece; kishit. In the card game: a picture of an old man with a crown is depicted, in terms of strength the card that stands after salt. 5 portable thing a or the best of people g, the best. The king of birds is an eagle. mm 6 Some word combinations include the meanings of a "head", "main", "big" means (some of these word combinations have become compound words and in circles. a person sitting on the throne and ruling the state is understood. The information given in the

notes helps students learn that words that differ in one sound have several meanings. As given in the definition of linguistic competence, the range of use of words used in oral speech causes confusion in students. It is necessary to prevent such situations in the oral speech of students during the course of the lesson. Task 2 in the 3rd grade mother tongue and reading literacy textbook focuses on the correct use of words in the text in order to form the competence of students to use words in their place, and to correct these mistakes by themselves. will encourage them not to use it. Task 2. There is a reporter who makes a lot of mistakes when writing. He always made mistakes in his newspaper articles. Below are some of the texts written by that reporter. They have one word wrong. You will have to find that word and correct it. The 21st century is a time of advanced technology. In the past 22 years, mankind has made discoveries that are difficult to comprehend. Caucasians have a custom of pouring the juice into a bowl reminiscent of the king of the ox. (In this sentence, the word "king" is used incorrectly. The word "king" in the sentence means "king". The word "horn" (horn of animals) should have been used in this sentence.)

In ancient times, the teachers who taught the children of kings lived in the palace. Teachers were highly respected. (In this sentence, the word "darz" is used incorrectly. The word "darz" means "crack", and in the text the word "darz" ("educational process") is used needed). To cook food, you need to pour it into a pot and heat it well. (In this sentence, the word "like" was used by mistake. The word "like" came in the meaning of towards. The word meaning "oil" (liquid) should have been used in the text.) y-lambs will crush cornstalks with magic. If not, they may find it very difficult to eat. (In this sentence, the word "jodu" is used incorrectly. The word "jodu" is used in the sense of magic. In the context, this word should have been used in the form of jodi (an instrument for cutting clover and stalks and preparing cattle feed) . Now people's wages are paid in plastic potatoes instead of paper money. (In this sentence, "potato" (in the meaning of vegetable). The word was omitted. In this sentence, the word "kartochka", i.e. a document in the form of paper and cardboard, should have been used. In task 1, only the words "horn" and "king" were analyzed through their dictionary meanings. The words "darz" and "dars", "yoq" and "yog", "kartochka" and "potato" given in the 2nd task were explained through analysis. These examples are given in the 3rd grade mother tongue and reading literacy textbook. Broader concepts of paronyms are explained in more detail in the Grade 4 Mother Tongue and Literacy textbook and higher grade textbooks. Paronymous words are often found in our speech. Many linguists have worked on paronyms. For example, Ahror Ma'rufov's book "Paronyms dictionary of the Uzbek language" contains explanations of the words analyzed above. In short, every pedagogue working in the educational system should direct all his knowledge and experience to improve the educational system. At the same time, we believe that the fair policy of the educational system conducted in our country will reveal special requirements for the educational process and special pedagogical relations.

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